

**“So much is available
electronically now
– it’s transformational.”**

Gwyn Bevan, Emeritus Professor
of Policy Analysis in the
Department of Management
at the London School of Economics
and Political Science

“How Did Britain Come to This?”, is Bevan’s latest book. Published open access, it had over 3,000 downloads in the first nine months.

Based on his experience, Bevan thinks technology and open access publishing have changed academia for the better. People can access and publish research more easily and freely, and research is more easily found and read. This leads to higher reader numbers, a more diverse readership and more citations. Academics gain a much higher profile, as does their research.

Bevan thinks that in the future, people who chose to publish through more traditional routes will be at a disadvantage. “Stuff you can access electronically will get read and cited, and stuff which you have to buy as a book or go to a library or access behind a paywall, will not do as well, will not have the same reach or citations.”

**How open access
and digital have been
transformational for Bevan**

Knowledge is easily and freely available. It’s at your fingertips, not shut away in a library, including important documents and primary research

The research process is faster and enriched by the depth and breadth of material that is available

People, academics and the general public, have much greater access to his research, amplifying its reach